

DESIGN, UTILIZATION, AND ACCEPTABILITY OF SOLAR-POWERED MOTORIZED WHEELBARROW

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ABSTRACT

This study explored the design, utilization, and acceptability of a solar-powered motorized wheelbarrow developed for instructional and hauling purposes. Utilizing the Project Development Method (PDM), the wheelbarrow was conceived, constructed, and evaluated by 75 respondents, including learners, teachers, farmers, and agricultural experts, selected through purposive sampling. Data collection employed a modified 22-item Likert-type questionnaire, originally developed by Bartolome (2019). The findings indicate that learners, teachers, and farmers rated the wheelbarrow as *"very much acceptable"* across various parameters, while experts deemed it *"acceptable."* Comparative analysis revealed significant differences in perceptions of design uniqueness, electrical components, functionality, and long-term usability, but consensus on the quality, safety, and user-friendliness of materials. The study concludes that the wheelbarrow is robust and effective as an educational tool, though areas such as design innovation and electrical integration require enhancement. Recommendations include improving maneuverability, increasing wheel size, refining the dumping mechanism, and integrating automation technology. This research highlights the importance of iterative design and user feedback in developing educational tools, advocating for broader application in agricultural and technical education to enhance practical learning experiences.

Keywords: *Motorized wheelbarrow, solar-powered, automation technology, agricultural education, instructional aid, iterative design*

INTRODUCTION

In the pursuit of advancing agricultural practices and educational methodologies, the development and integration of innovative tools have become paramount. One such innovative tool is the solar-powered motorized wheelbarrow, designed to ease the transportation of farm inputs, planting materials, and tools. This innovation not only aims to save time and energy but also seeks to enhance the educational experience of learners engaged in Agri-Crops Production.

Agricultural education is a critical component in fostering the next generation of farmers and agricultural scientists. However, traditional tools often require significant physical exertion, which can detract from the educational experience and discourage participation, particularly among female students. The conventional one-wheeled wheelbarrow, for instance, demands considerable physical strength to balance and maneuver, leading to fatigue and decreased productivity (Ashwini & Robinson, 2022).

In contrast, the proposed solar-powered motorized wheelbarrow incorporates a four-wheeled design, back-driven motorization, and front maneuverability, which collectively reduce physical effort and improve stability on uneven terrain. This design is anticipated to be especially beneficial in promoting gender equality by making agricultural tasks more accessible to all learners, regardless of physical strength (Price, 2020).

The integration of solar power as the energy source for the motorized wheelbarrow aligns with the global shift towards renewable energy and sustainable practices. Solar energy, derived from photovoltaic (PV) systems, is a clean, renewable resource that reduces reliance on fossil fuels and minimizes carbon footprints (Siksnyte-Butkiene et al., 2020). By utilizing solar power, the wheelbarrow not only operates with zero emissions but also serves as a practical educational tool that highlights the importance of renewable energy in agricultural innovations. This aligns with the United Nations Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs), particularly those focused on energy decarbonization and sustainable industry (Sachs et al., 2019).

The design of the solar-powered motorized wheelbarrow draws inspiration from various innovations in wheelbarrow technology. Previous designs have included auxiliary storage bins for tools (Milo), conversion kits for multi-utility use (Celli), and powered wheelbarrows with control mechanisms (Cook & Otto, 2020). However, most of these designs are powered by fuel or electricity, which still contributes to environmental degradation. In contrast, the current study aims to harness solar energy, thereby promoting ecological sustainability and reducing overall energy consumption (Kabir et al., 2018).

The potential impact of this innovation extends beyond the practical benefits of easing transportation tasks. By incorporating ergonomic and anthropomorphic considerations, the solar-powered motorized wheelbarrow is designed to suit the average Filipino learner, enhancing comfort and usability. Additionally, the inclusion of a linear

actuator for automated dumping further reduces physical strain, making the tool user-friendly and efficient (Michel, 2015).

To sum it up, the solar-powered motorized wheelbarrow represents a significant step forward in both agricultural education and sustainable practice. It addresses the physical demands of traditional wheelbarrows, promotes gender equality, and integrates renewable energy technology, making it a valuable instructional material in Agri-Crops Production.

Hence, this study aims to explore the design, development, and utilization of this innovative tool, providing a practical solution to improve the quality of agricultural education and contribute to sustainable agricultural practices in the Philippines.

Research Questions

This study aimed to design and utilize a solar-powered motorized wheelbarrow as an instructional material in Agri-Crops Production. It also aimed to determine its acceptability.

Specifically, the study sought to answer the following questions:

1. What are the processes involved in designing and constructing a solar-powered motorized wheelbarrow?
2. What is the level of acceptability of the developed solar-powered motorized wheelbarrow as evaluated by the respondents in terms of:
 - a. design and construction,
 - b. functionality,
 - c. Safety,
 - d. durability,
 - e. instructional applicability
3. Is there a significant difference in the level of acceptability of the developed solar-powered motorized wheelbarrow as perceived by the respondents?

METHODOLOGY

Research Design

The Project Development Method (PDM) was used in this study, and the researcher conceived the design and specifications of the Solar-powered Motorized Wheelbarrow for instructional material and hauling purposes.

Respondents and Sampling Procedure

The respondents in this study consisted of twenty (20) TVE Agri-Crops production and Animal Production learners, fifteen (15) teachers of Gamu Agri-Fishery School, fifteen (15) farmers/ gardeners, and fifteen (15) experts from the Department of

Agriculture (DA). Also included in the group were ten (10) farmers/ garden hobbyists in the locality. They were selected as respondents through a purposive sampling technique.

Data Gathering Procedure

The project was developed following a series of phases which included designing, constructing/fabricating, testing, and evaluating the output.

Adaption of Research Instruments. To gather data about the evaluation of the four groups of respondents on the designed solar-powered motorized wheelbarrow, the researcher adopted the 22-item Likert-type questionnaire, Bartolome (2019) utilized in his study. Revisions were made to the questionnaire to suit the objectives of the study.

Identification of the Respondents. The target respondents are Agri-Crops Production learners of Gamu Agri-Fishery School. The list of learners will be used as the sampling frame for the random selection of the respondents in the study. Further, the list of TVE Teachers from the same school are also respondents and will also be randomly selected. Also, Garden hobbyists from the locality were part of the group of respondents. Lastly, the Expert Group was the personnel of DA-CVRC located at San Felipe, City of Ilagan, Isabela.

Administration of the Research Instrument. After identifying the 15 randomly selected teacher respondents 20 randomly selected learners, 15 farmer/ gardeners, and 15 experts, the survey questionnaire will be administered to prompt information for the evaluation of the four groups of respondents in the study.

Scoring, Analysis, and Interpretation of data. After the administration of the different instruments, scores were tabulated in a worksheet using the spreadsheet, which served as the basis for the statistical treatment of the data to answer the research problems. Analysis and interpretation of results followed, after which, conclusions and recommendations were made based on the findings of the study.

Data Gathering Instruments

A portion of the questionnaires used in Engr. Elmer A. Bartolome's master's thesis titled, "*Development and Acceptability of an Industrial Motor Control System Trainer*," at Isabela State University, was modified by the researcher with permission. The modified instrument was divided into two parts: Part I dealt with the respondents' profile, which included their age, area of expertise, or profession, and Part II contained the standards for evaluating the acceptability of the developed solar-powered motorized wheelbarrow in terms of design and construction, functionality and efficiency, durability, safety, and instructional applicability. It used a 5-point questionnaire of this kind to assess whether the solar-powered motorized wheelbarrow was acceptable. Part III sought the comments or recommendations of the respondents based on their observations.

The collected data were tallied and analyzed using the scale below:

Rating	Scale	Qualitative Description	Interpretation Description
5	4.20- 5.00	Strongly Agree	VeryMuch Acceptable
4	3.40- 4.19	Moderately Agree	Acceptable
3	2.60-3.39	Agree	Moderately Acceptable
2	1.80-2.59	Moderately Disagree	Fairly Acceptable
1	1.00-1.79	Strongly Disagree	Revise/Not Acceptable

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Project Description

The solar-powered motorized wheelbarrow designed by the researcher has unique features compared to the design of conventional wheelbarrows available in the Philippine market. The design innovates mobility while maintaining the traditional look and feel of the wheelbarrow, considering the parameters for farm tools and equipment, availability of resources, and functionality of the wheelbarrow. The size was based on the parameter of a conventional 4 cu. ft. capacity and 156 cm. in length from the bucket's tip to the wheelbarrow's handle. The design of a solar-powered motorized wheelbarrow adopts the parameters Bureau of Agricultural and Fisheries Engineering (BAFE) of the Department of Education Reference Manual of Agricultural and Fisheries Machinery and Equipment Section V, general provisions such as the use of Solar Panel and DC Motor as prime mover, and the inclusion of gender fairness in the design of the equipment.

Considering all these factors, the design was conceptualized: a conventional bucket (60 liters capacity), a frame that aligned the motor and the bucket, and a maneuverable handle with a mechanism attached to the front wheels. The motor is located at the base of the frame near the rear wheels, allowing the sprocket and chain tension mechanism to mobilize the wheelbarrow. The motor capacity can be assumed to carry a load of up to 300 lb. The Control system is at the dashboard framed at the handle of the wheelbarrow with its throttle controller at the right handle. The handle has an ergonomic grip, which gives comfort to the user. The design also considered the electrical mechanism at the same time the anthropomorphic parameter of the project, the panel is located on top of the wheelbarrow framed with sturdy tubular steel allowing it to harvest the highest possible sun heat converting to electrical energy and with approximate clearance considering the height of a Filipino learner thus giving enough shade to the user. The added feature of the wheelbarrow is the dumping mechanism using a linear actuator attached to the base frame and the bucket frame, this works when the rocket switch of the actuator is manipulated resulting in either pushing up or pulling downward

the bucket, this gives ease of doing tasks. It can lift to 150 pounds of loads. The design resembles a small cart with an attached solar panel and mechanism.

Project Structure

The Solar-Powered Motorized Wheelbarrow consists of four major components namely, mainframe assembly, dumping mechanism assembly, Solar panel Assembly, and electrical components assembly.

The developed solar-powered motorized wheelbarrow has a height of 180 cm from the wheelbase up to the top of the solar panel and 90 cm from the wheelbase up to the handle of the wheelbarrow. It has a width of 50 cm from its main body and 80 cm from the solar panel, 180 cm length from the handle to the bucket end, and an average weight of 35 kg-38 kg. The designed Solar-Powered Motorized Wheelbarrow is an innovative idea considering the ease of hauling and transporting small loads compared to the conventional wheelbarrow.

Figure 1. The Solar-Powered Motorized Wheelbarrow

Figure 2. Dashboard and Handle Structure of the Designed Solar-Powered Wheelbarrow

Project Capabilities and Limitations

The solar-powered motorized wheelbarrow can make it easy to transport or haul agricultural inputs and harvests, based on the transportation capabilities of the wheelbarrow, it can load up to 70 kgs or an average of 50 kgs to transport in even road conditions. The designer finds it gender-fair, making cozy transportation without the stress of pushing a conventional wheelbarrow because it is equipped with a motor with 4 wheelbases. An added feature is the dumping mechanism, which unloads by manipulating only the switch without the effort to dump the bucket like in a conventional wheelbarrow. Its user-friendly dashboard displays the solar charge controller to check the voltage during charging time, the watt and voltage meter to check the voltage upon use, and switches to load and unload, move forward and reverse. It has a speed controller (throttle) to speed up and down.

The developed solar-powered motorized wheelbarrow is limited only as an instructional material to be utilized by the Agri-Crops Production learners of Gamu Agri-Fishery School during their laboratory to ease their effort of hauling.

Operation and Testing Procedure

After constructing the designed Solar-Powered Motorized Wheelbarrow, the project underwent testing to determine the salient features, performance, and technical specifications and its general acceptability in terms of its design and construction, durability, functionality, safety, and instructional applicability.

A. Operation Procedure

1. Detail the parts of the solar-powered motorized wheelbarrow.
2. Switch on the ignition switch in the wheelbarrow dashboard, and check if all the controllers are working.
3. Place a load in the bucket (seedlings, stakes, mix soil media, etc.)
4. Lightly press the throttle lever, to accelerate the movement of the wheelbarrow.
5. Maneuver the wheelbarrow at a corner or cross sections of pathways.
6. Unload the wheelbarrow bucket's load by switching the rocket switch at the unload function.
7. Switch back the rocket switch to return the bucket to its normal position.
8. Maneuver and return to the starting station.

B. Testing Procedure

1. Functionality Test

The solar-powered motorized wheelbarrow was designed and then put through different testing procedures to check its functionality across various parameters related to its operation. During the testing phase, the evaluators assessed the ease of operation with controllers and switches, as well as the loading and unloading capabilities. The wheelbarrow speed controller, or throttle, was utilized to speed up and slow down, while the forward and reverse switches helped with movement. Similarly, the load and unload switch of the linear actuator was used to unload the load from the wheelbarrow bucket.

The charging capacity of the solar batteries was also tested, a day before the field testing of the equipment, the batteries were charged for about 405 minutes (6 hours +) from 8:45 am to 2:30 pm in partly cloudy weather, and the batteries reached 26+ volts upon being tested using a voltmeter as shown in Table 6. During the field testing, the battery voltage declined slightly with an approximate capacity of 24 +- voltage.

The equipment was also tested as to its maneuverability feature, evaluators found it acceptable to the group of experts which means adjustments to its feature should be made for better performance. The result is significantly very much sufficient for the groups of teachers and learners and adequate for the groups of experts and gardeners regarding electrical and mechanical efficiency.

Figure 3. A learner-respondent manipulating the switches and controller of the solar-powered motorized wheelbarrow

2. Durability Test

The solar-powered motorized wheelbarrow has an ideal maximum load capacity of 60-70 kg in a perfect topography based on Figure 18. Based on the conducted series of tests by the evaluators, loaded with about the standard capacity of 50 kgs, the battery runs for about 100 minutes continuously specially in D.A. CVRC, and found out only less than 1-2 volt difference from the volt reading before it was tested. The equipment runs in partly hilly and uneven topography areas in D.A. CVRC, gardens, and the school.

Figure 4. A teacher evaluator sits on the wheelbarrow bucket to check the durability of the wheelbarrow's structure and its load limit capacity.

3. Safety Test

The solar-powered motorized wheelbarrow comes with safety features that include the use of insulation materials for wiring and the installation of controllers and switches to enhance safety during usage. Additionally, it is equipped with a brake mechanism that slows down the movement, especially in areas with slopes, to prevent accidents.

Project Evaluation

Level of Acceptability of the Developed Solar-Powered Motorized Wheelbarrow

The table presents the level of acceptability of the Developed Solar-Powered Motorized Wheelbarrow in terms of Design and Construction, Functionality, Durability, Safety, and Instructional Applicability.

As to its design and construction, the Learners gave the highest overall mean score with the developed Solar-Powered Motorized Wheelbarrow with a mean of 4.59 and a standard deviation of 0.5336. The learners found that the product is very much acceptable. On the other hand, the Experts rated it with a mean of 4.05 and a standard deviation of 0.6757. Experts found the product to be acceptable when it comes to its design and construction.

Table 2. Level of Acceptability of the Developed Solar-Powered Motorized Wheelbarrow

Learners			
Indicators	Mean	Sd	Description
Design and Construction	4.59	0.5336	Very Much acceptable
Functionality	4.75	0.4352	Very Much acceptable
Durability	4.55	0.5344	Very Much acceptable
Safety	4.50	0.5412	Very Much acceptable
Instructional Applicability	4.75	0.4904	Very Much acceptable
Overall Mean	4.628		Very Much acceptable
Teachers			
Indicators	Mean	Sd	Description
Design and Construction	4.35	0.6876	Very Much acceptable
Functionality	4.48	0.6850	Very Much acceptable
Durability	4.24	0.8021	Very Much acceptable
Safety	4.33	0.7229	Very Much acceptable
Instructional Applicability	4.68	0.5365	Very Much acceptable
Overall Mean	4.416		Very Much acceptable
Experts			
Indicators	Mean	Sd	Description
Design and Construction	4.05	0.6757	Acceptable
Functionality	3.84	0.5462	Acceptable
Durability	4.02	0.2601	Acceptable

Safety	3.99	0.4791	Acceptable
Instructional Applicability	4.05	0.4746	Acceptable
Overall Mean	3.99		Acceptable
Gardeners			
Indicators	Mean	Sd	Description
Design and Construction	4.27	0.5593	Acceptable
Functionality	4.17	0.5544	Acceptable
Durability	4.13	0.5477	Acceptable
Safety	4.31	0.5456	Acceptable
Instructional Applicability	4.13	0.5357	Acceptable
Overall Mean	4.20		Very Much Acceptable

For its functionality, both the learners and the teachers found the developed Solar-Powered Motorized Wheelbarrow to be very much acceptable having a mean of 4.75 and 4.48, respectively while both the Experts and the Gardeners found the developed Solar-Powered Motorized Wheelbarrow to be acceptable. This implies that the product received consistently positive feedback from the respondents.

Concerning Durability, the learners gave the highest overall mean equivalent of 4.55 and they found the developed Solar-Powered Motorized Wheelbarrow to be very much acceptable, however, both experts and gardeners found the developed Solar-Powered Motorized Wheelbarrow to be acceptable with a mean score of 4.02 as the lowest mean. This indicates that while learners found the Solar-Powered Motorized Wheelbarrow to be very much acceptable in terms of durability (as indicated by the high mean score of 4.55), the perspectives of both experts and gardeners resulted in a lower mean score of 4.02, suggesting a slightly lower level of acceptance from these groups.

The learners, teachers, and gardeners found the safety of the developed Solar-Powered Motorized Wheelbarrow to be very much acceptable with the highest mean of 4.50 coming from the learners. The experts deemed the developed Solar-Powered Motorized Wheelbarrow to be acceptable giving a mean score of 3.99. This means that while learners, teachers, and gardeners highly rated the safety of the Solar-Powered Motorized Wheelbarrow, experts provided a slightly lower mean score, indicating that they considered the safety features to be acceptable but potentially with some room for improvement.

In terms of Instructional Applicability, all respondents, which includes learners, teachers, and potentially others, unanimously found the Solar-Powered Motorized Wheelbarrow to be very much acceptable. The learners and teachers, who are likely end-users and educators, provided the highest scores with a mean of 4.75 and 4.68,

respectively, emphasizing its practicality and instructional value. The emphasis on practicality and instructional value suggests that these groups see the technology as not only acceptable but also beneficial for educational purposes.

Comparison in the Level of Acceptability of the Developed Solar-Powered Motorized Wheelbarrow as Perceived by the Groups of Respondents

Table 3. Comparison in the Level of Acceptability of the Developed Solar-Powered Motorized Wheelbarrow as Perceived by the Respondents

Design and Construction	F-Value	p-Value	Decision	Remark
Over-all Look	8.3337	0.0001	Reject H ₀	Significant
Components and parts	1.5792	0.2036	Accept H ₀	Not Significant
Uniqueness of design	3.7414	0.0156	Reject H ₀	Significant
Ergonomic and Anthropomorphic	2.6947	0.0538	Accept H ₀	Not Significant
Electrical Components	3.3908	0.0235	Reject H ₀	Significant
Functionality	F-Value	p-Value	Description	Description
Instructional Purpose	10.3763	0.0000	Reject H ₀	Significant
Related Activities	7.5468	0.0002	Reject H ₀	Significant
Over-all Performance	6.49980	0.0007	Reject H ₀	Significant
Efficiency of electrical and Mechanical Components	13.0936	0.0000	Reject H ₀	Significant
Dumping Mechanism	6.2714	0.0009	Reject H ₀	Significant
Durability	F-Value	p-Value	Description	Description
Materials used	1.9963	0.1239	Accept H ₀	Not Significant
Frame Assembly, solar panel, electrical components, and mechanical	3.5167	0.0203	Reject H ₀	Significant
The material's usability for a longer period	3.2123	0.0290	Reject H ₀	Significant
Safety	F-Value	p-Value	Description	Description
Safe to use and User-Friendly	1.9128	0.1369	Accept H ₀	Not Significant
Condition of the parts and components	1.0199	0.3901	Accept H ₀	Not Significant

Installed Electrical components	6.286	0.0009	Reject H ₀	Significant
Various materials in construction	2.746	0.0519	Accept H ₀	Not Significant
Dumping Mechanism	4.4455	0.0069	Reject H ₀	Significant
Instructional Applicability	F-Value	p-Value	Description	Description
Effective for instructional and farm use	7.7297	0.0002	Reject H ₀	Significant
Suitable for ACP and AP	11.2864	0.0000	Reject H ₀	Significant
Improves Teaching-learning process	6.0249	0.0012	Reject H ₀	Significant
Operation and manipulation according to needed activity	14.4638	0.0000	Reject H ₀	Significant

The table presents the comparison of the level of acceptability of the developed solar-powered motorized wheelbarrow as perceived by the respondents (Learners, Teachers, Farmers/Gardeners, and Experts).

As presented in the table, in terms of Components and Parts, Ergonomic and Anthropomorphic Features, the p -values are greater than 0.05, hence the null hypothesis is accepted. This indicates that there is no statistically significant difference in the perception of the components and parts among the respondents. The different groups perceive the components and parts, and ergonomic and anthropomorphic similarly. About the Over-all Look, Uniqueness of Design, and Electrical Components, it was found that the p -value is less than 0.05, therefore, the null hypothesis is rejected. This suggests that there is a statistically significant difference in the perception of the overall look among the respondents. The design's overall look, uniqueness of design, and electrical components are perceived differently by learners, teachers, farmers/gardeners, and experts.

Additionally, the analysis of the functionality criteria indicates that respondents have significantly different perceptions across all evaluated aspects: instructional purpose, related activities, overall performance, efficiency of electrical and mechanical components, and the dumping mechanism. All computed p -values are less than 0.05, thus the null hypothesis is accepted. The strong statistical significance in all these areas suggests diverse expectations and opinions among the various respondent groups.

On the other hand, there are mixed perceptions when it comes to the durability of the product. The developed solar-powered motorized wheelbarrow is generally perceived to be made from quality materials, indicating a good foundation for durability. However, significant differences in perceptions about the durability of specific components (Mainframe Assembly, Bucket Frame assembly, Solar Panel Frame Assembly, and Electrical Circuit Assembly) and the long-term usability of materials point to areas that require attention. Specifically, in terms of the Materials Used, it can be gleaned from the

table that the computed ρ -value is greater than 0.05, thus, the acceptance of the null hypothesis.

This means that there is no significant difference in the perception of the materials used. Generally, respondents agree on the quality of the materials used in the wheelbarrow. This suggests that the materials chosen for construction are deemed acceptable across different user groups, indicating a satisfactory level of durability in terms of material quality. As to its Mainframe Assembly, Bucket Frame Assembly, Solar Panel Frame Assembly, and Electrical Circuit Assembly usability for a longer period, the null hypothesis is being rejected since the computed ρ -values have lower value than 0.05. There is a significant difference in the perception of the durability of these components. The variability in respondents' opinions suggests that some user groups may have concerns or different experiences regarding the durability of the Mainframe Assembly, Bucket Frame Assembly, Solar Panel Frame Assembly, and Electrical Circuit Assembly. This indicates potential areas where improvements might be needed to ensure consistent durability and reliability across all components for all users.

The safety analysis reveals mixed perceptions among respondents. There is a general agreement on the overall safety and user-friendliness of the product, the condition of the parts and components, and the safety of the various materials used in construction. All these components showed ρ -values greater than 0.05 accepting the null hypothesis which means that there is no significant difference in the perceptions of the respondents when it comes to these components. This indicates that the different groups generally agree that the parts and components are in good condition and meet safety standards, the product is broadly considered safe and easy to use and the general agreement on the safety of the materials used. On the contrary, significant differences in the perceptions of the respondents were found in terms of the installed electrical components' safety and the dumping mechanism's safety. This suggests that there are notable concerns or varying opinions regarding the safety of this feature among different user groups or there is a need for further assessment and possibly redesigning or enhancing these aspects to ensure they meet safety expectations and alleviate any user concerns.

Lastly, the analysis of the instructional applicability criteria reveals that respondents have significantly different perceptions across all evaluated aspects. As shown in the table, all the computed ρ -values are less than 0.05 indicating the rejection of the null hypothesis. This also indicates a strong statistical significance, suggesting diverse opinions on the practicality and usability of the wheelbarrow for various activities. This therefore implies that the developed solar-powered motorized wheelbarrow is viewed quite variably by different user groups regarding its instructional effectiveness and usability.

Conclusions

From the above findings, this study concludes that the solar-powered motorized wheelbarrow is generally well-received among learners, teachers, and gardeners, with high ratings for its design, construction, functionality, durability, safety, and instructional applicability. Experts, while positive, had a slightly less favorable view, highlighting areas for potential improvement. The consensus on safety and material quality suggests that the wheelbarrow is both user-friendly and robust, though varied perceptions of design uniqueness, electrical components, and long-term usability imply a need for further refinement in these areas. These results emphasize the importance of iterative design and user feedback in developing educational tools, suggesting that future iterations should focus on enhancing innovative features and electrical integration to meet diverse user expectations fully. On the whole, the positive reception of the solar-powered motorized wheelbarrow among a diverse group of users implies that such innovative tools can significantly enhance practical learning in agricultural education.

Recommendations

Based on the findings and conclusions, the following recommendations are offered:

1. The current design's maneuverability should be enhanced.
 2. Bigger sizes of wheels both front and rear wheels should be used to give higher base clearance ready for any terrain ground.
 3. The dumping mechanism should be enhanced to even stepper dumping.
 4. Balance should be incorporated for easier mobility even without load.
 5. This developed solar-powered motorized wheelbarrow should be upgraded with automation technology and incorporate the use of AI in handling or moving.
 6. This developed motorized wheelbarrow trainer should be introduced in other specializations like building construction courses, both in Technical Vocational Schools and in TESDA schools.
 7. Further research should be conducted to continuously improve the trainer.
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Compliance with Ethical Standards

The author ensured compliance with ethical standards by obtaining informed consent from the participants, guaranteeing their freedom to withdraw from the study at any time. The anonymity of the respondents was maintained to protect their privacy, and measures were taken to safeguard their well-being throughout the research process. The study was conducted without any conflict of interest, plagiarism was strictly avoided, and there was no bias in the interpretation of the findings. The results were solely used for research purposes, upholding the integrity and credibility of the study.

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